

**CENTRE OF DRYLAND AGRICULTURE (CDA),
BAYERO UNIVERSITY, KANO**
...An Africa Centre of Excellence

In collaboration with

**DEPARTMENT OF FISHERIES AND AQUACULTURE,
FACULTY OF AGRICULTURE,
BAYERO UNIVERSITY, KANO**

**TRAINING WORKSHOP FOR
WOMEN AND YOUTH**

ON

**FISH PRODUCTION,
PROCESSING AND
MARKETING**

TRAINING MANUAL

FOREWORD

One of the major challenges faced by the Nigerian Government is the increasing number of unemployed youths in a country where human and infrastructural development has continuously been submerged by social crisis and violence. It is an established fact that in most cases, these crises are planned and executed by unemployed youths who wanted to be heard by the larger society. Worrysome however, is the reality that victims of the violence are usually innocent highly productive citizens including women.

It is an established fact that agriculture (aquaculture inclusive) is the sector with the largest capacity and resources that can be tapped by the Federal Government to curb youths' restiveness and empower women through appropriate engagement of the teeming population of these youths (including graduates) and women in our midst. Fish production is one of the enterprises in agriculture that can gainfully occupy women and youths so as to strengthen Nigeria's agricultural transformation agenda and subsequently hasten the attainment of some vital aspects of the Millennium Development Goals (MDGs) - poverty reduction and food security.

The selected women and youths for this programme will undergo intensive practical and theoretical training to equip them on 'hand-on skills' in fish production, processing and marketing. I hope other corporate institutions will take advantage of our manpower and facilities in the department and partner with us for the training of many other Nigerian women and youths so as to empower them economically and thus harness their energy productively. I am sure that relevant bodies involved in agricultural training and development in the country will find this training manual a valuable reference material.

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MODULE 1

FISH CULTURE AND MANAGEMENT

1.1 INTRODUCTION TO FISH CULTURE

DEFINITION AND IMPORTANCE

Fish production involves the culture of both fin fish and non-fin fish in a water enclosure. Fish production can be done in marine, brackish and freshwater. The most commonly species cultured in Nigeria include African Catfish, Tilapia, Common carp, *Heterotis* and *Gymnarchus*. Nigeria is the largest fish producer in Africa with output of over 15,489 tons per annum. Annual fish consumption is 16.1kg per capita globally (FAO, 2016). Nigerians consume more than 1.36 million MT per annum, imports making up 740,000MT of the fish supply. About 60% of people in developing countries depend on fish as source animal protein (FAO, 2015).

Fish culture involves the controlled cultivation and harvesting of fish for either family consumption or sales in the market. Although fish culture is over forty years old in Nigeria, it is yet to develop fully when compared with arable agriculture and livestock production. A wide range of practices exists in culturing fish. Fish can be cultured in marine water (seawater), brackish water (mixture of sea and freshwater i.e. lagoons) or freshwater (rivers, streams and lakes in the inland). Depending on the facilities designed to serve as enclosures in rearing, fish can be grown in earthen ponds, concrete tanks, cages, pens, or run-ways. The level of management practices can make a fish farm to be extensive, semi-intensive or intensive system. When species combinations are taken into consideration, culture systems can be either monoculture (rearing only one type of fish) or polyculture (rearing two or more species of fish together). A fishpond is an enclosure (earthen or concrete) built to retain water for the purpose of growing fish. Growing fish in ponds from which they cannot escape allows feeding, breeding, growing and harvesting of the fish in a well-planned way.

Fish culture is important for the following reasons:

- i. To provide fish protein to the teeming population. Most Nigerians find their protein needs in cheap fisheries products
- ii. To provide employment to people, especially youths. Through fish culture youths can be self employed and be empowered economically.
- iii. Fish caught in rivers are seasonal. Aquaculture provides the means of getting fish all year round.
- iv. Waste lands can be modified for fish culture

1.2. POND CULTURE SYSTEMS

Fish ponds can be classified mainly using the following criteria:

1. Construction design
2. Fish culture practices
3. Location of production
4. Scale of production

Construction Design

i. Earthen Ponds: These are constructed by digging soil in a carefully selected site that is good enough to retain water for fish culture. Where the soil structure is weak to retain adequate water, dug out earthen ponds can be reinforced with concrete to make it suitable for fish culture.

Figure 1: Earthen Pond

ii. Concrete/Embarkment Ponds: This is pond constructed on the ground that is above the ground surface with concrete wall. Concrete ponds can be used to raise fish in a place with porous or sandy soil.

Figure 2: Concrete or Cement Block Tank

iii. Barrage Ponds: Barrage ponds are constructed by building a dike across a natural stream running in a low valley. The ponds are therefore like small conservation dams with the advantage that they are easy to construct. The wall ensures enough water retention for fish growth. However, it is difficult to keep wild fish out and a lot of feed added to the pond may be lost because of the current. A properly built barrage pond overflows only under unusual circumstances.

Figure 3: Barrage Pond

iv. Diversion Pond: Pond supplied by water diverted from a river/stream through a channel. Such a pond is also known as a Relief Pond

Figure 4: Diversion Pond

v. Rosary Pond: When ponds are built in a string and each drains into the other and are all managed as a single unit due to their water connection, they are called Rosary Ponds or **Parallel Ponds:** These are ponds located in an area with each having its own inlet and outlet.

Figure 5: Rosary or Parallel Pond

Fish Culture Practices

Pond can be classified as being monoculture or polyculture.

i. Monoculture: This is the practice of culturing only one type of fish in a pond unit. Under monoculture, a farmer may grow only Tilapia in the pond. He will be able to know more about the management of Tilapia than other species he is not growing.

Figure 6: Monoculture- Growing only one type of fish

ii. Polyculture: This is the practice of culturing more than one species of fish in the same pond. Fish yield under polyculture can be higher and foods in the pond properly utilized, since the different fish species exploit food at different levels in the pond.

Figure 7: Polyculture – Growing two or more species of fish in the same pond

1.2.3 Location of Production

i. Homestead/Backyard Ponds: This is a fishpond that is managed to augment family protein intake. The size of such a pond could vary according to land space available e.g.5x5x1m.

ii. Fish Farms: This, usually have an area of land not less than half hectare under culture. Such a farm will demand more attention from the fish farmer, since income generation is the major purpose behind its establishment.

1.2.4 Scale of production

i. Subsistence production: These are mainly small-scale fish ponds meant only for family consumption. Occasionally some of the fish may be sold or given away free. Only family labour is used, no hire labour is employed.

ii. Commercial Production: These are fish ponds built for commercial production. Profit sense is high. Labour is employed for operation, production records are kept and production is mainly target for market.

1.3 FISH PRODUCTION SYSTEMS

Depending on the level of management inputs, especially in feeding, fertilization and liming, pond culture systems can be classified as extensive, semi-intensive or intensive.

i. Extensive Culture System: When food base in a pond is exclusively naturally occurring without supplementation (either by feeds or fertilizer), the culture system is extensive.

ii. Semi-Intensive Culture System: In this system, there is occasional supplementary feeds addition and natural productivity is augmented with manure.

iii. Intensive Culture System: This demands the highest level of management input. Feeds and fertilizers are intensively applied following appropriate recommended rates. Suitable liming materials like agricultural lime are also applied to stimulate productivity and disinfect the pond of parasite and diseases. Fish grow very fast when intensively managed and grow least in extensive management.

iv. Integrated aquaculture system: This system is a combination of the culture of aquatic organisms (e.g. fish) with other forms of agriculture such as poultry, piggery, duck-rearing, cattle, goat-rearing and rice/vegetables in such a way that some of the by-products and wastes of these plants and animals can still be recycled for either direct or indirect consumption by fish. The advantages of integrated culture are:

- i. There is no need for expensive fishing gears. Simple drainage/harvest methods are used.
- ii. Low operating and maintenance cost.
- iii. Multiple uses of land that would otherwise have been useless
- iv. Saves feeding costs.
- v. Multiple harvests of commodities in the same piece of land
- vi. Make for effective monitoring of both fish and other commodities within in the same range.

Figure 8: Integrated Poultry-Fish culture with cage on an earthen pond

1.4 COMMONLY CULTURED FISH SPECIES

Generally the purpose of rearing fish is to have enough to eat and generate additional income especially in commercial farms. Not all fish species perform creditably well in culture. For a profitable venture, the fish farmer's ideal candidate species must have either of these qualities: -

- i. Fast grower e.g. *Heterobranchus*
- ii. Accept and utilize properly, supplementary feeds e.g. *Tilapia*
- iii. Must be hardy and resistance to disease, e.g. *Clarias*
- iv. Must be tolerant to poor water quality e.g. *Clarias*
- v. The fish must be easy to breed in captivity. E.g. *Tilapia*
- vi. It must attract low production cost (*Tilapia/Clarias*)
- vii. Acceptable and marketable to consumers. E.g. *Carp and Heterotis, Tilapia and Clarias*.

In Nigeria, certain fish species are found only in freshwater bodies (that is rivers and lakes) and do very well under culture. Some other species inhabit the marine environment, but can be cultured in brackish water (Lagoons and estuaries). The commonly cultured freshwater fish species in Nigeria are shown in Table 1.

Table: 1 Commonly Cultured Fish Species in Freshwater Ponds in Nigeria

<i>Common Name</i>	<i>Scientific Name</i>	<i>Hausa Name</i>
1. Tilapia*	<i>Oreochromis niloticus</i>	Karfasa
2. Mud Cat-fish*	<i>Clarias lazera gariepinus</i>	Tarwada
3. Common Carp*	<i>Cyprinus carpio</i>	
4. Spotted Cat-fish**	<i>Synodontis filamentosus</i>	Kurungu
5. Red mud cat-fish*	<i>Heterobranchus bi-dorsalis</i>	Mari
6. Niger perch * *	<i>Lates niloticus</i>	Giwan ruwa
7. Grey cat-fish* *	<i>Chrysichthys nigrodigitatus</i>	
8. African bony tongue*	<i>Heterotis niloticus</i>	Bargi
9. Trunk-fish* *	<i>Gymnarchus niloticus</i>	Yauni
10. Cat-fish* *	<i>Bagrus bayad</i>	Ragon ruwa
11. African Carp* *	<i>Lates niloticus</i>	
12. Moon fish* *	<i>Citharinus citherus</i>	Paliya

*Fingerlings readily available in hatcheries

**Fingerlings not readily available in hatcheries but can be collected from rivers and lakes.

1.5 FISH CULTURE FACILITIES

INTRODUCTION

The term ‘Aquaculture’ or ‘fish culture’ covers all forms of cultivation of aquatic animals and plants in fresh-, brackish- and saltwater. Aquaculture has the same objective as agriculture, namely, to increase the production of food above the level that would be produced naturally. These are the materials used in fisheries. They include the materials that are used in holding fish, those used in channelling water in and out of the fish pond and those used in handling fish in all stages of production.

PRODUCTION FACILITIES

There are different types of facilities that are used in raising or holding fish, they include:

i. Earthen Pond

Earth Ponds may be dug into the ground; they may be partly above or below original ground level. Slopes and bottom should be well packed during construction to prevent erosion and seepage. Soil should contain a minimum of 25% clay. Rocks, grass, branches and other undesirable objects should be eliminated from the dikes. Generally they are not constructed with cementing materials.

Figure 9: A large Earthen Pond

ii. Concrete pond

A concrete tank is the tank produced with vibrated block 6 or 9 inches, in which the holes are filled with pure concrete to fortify it. A 6ft X 15ft X 4ft concrete tank can successfully raise a 1000 fish to maturity. A connection of 6 to 12 tanks of the same dimension, connected through the individual outlets, water are channel to the concrete tank through pressure pipe from overhead water tank or directly from a well, borehole etc. However 4-inches pipe are used for outlet purposes.

iii. Plastic/ Fiber glass

A plastic or fiber glass tank as the name implies is a tank made up of plastic or fiber glass materials. The fiber glass normally ensures the strength of the tank as well as ensuring there are no leaks. If the tank has a leak after construction, empty the tank and let it dry. Then reapply more fiber glass to the interior of the tank. The plastic tanks come in different shapes and sizes. This depends on the intended stocking quantity of the farmer.

Figure 10: Plastic Tanks

iv. Tarpaulin

This type of fish holding accessories are constructed to depend on strong iron or wooden frames. The tarpaulin is normally suspended down between the frame and create a container that will hold water. It is flexible as well as collapsible. It comes in different shapes and sizes.

Figure 11: A Tarpaulin Tank

v. Cages/ Pen

Cages or pens are not very popular in Nigeria. They are fish rearing structures that are used in large bodies of waters. Cages can be constructed with bamboo or plastic materials and attached aside floats that will facilitate buoyancy. Pens on the other hand are made up of netting materials of different types.

Figure 12: A Stationary Cage Facility for Fish Culture

vi. Wooden tanks

Wooden tanks are not very common in Fish culture. They are normally created as temporary holding structures. The wooden box is normally covered internally with polythene to prevent water from touching the wood. It can be created in different size.

Figure 13: A Wooden Tank for Culturing Fish

1.6 POINTS TO NOTE ON THE FACILITIES

i. Earthen pond

- Fish get more natural food in the water body.
- Water source is normally natural and less expensive even if to be supplemented.
- Sorting of fish is difficult.
- Difficult to harvest.

ii. Concrete pond

- Harvesting is easy
- Water quality maintenance is also easy
- Feeding is intensive since fish depends on supplementary feed.
- Pond construction is expensive

iii. Plastic/ Fibre glass

- It is transferable.
- Harvesting is easy.
- Cannot keep many fish
- Weather affects fish growth.

iv. Tarpaulin

- It is collapsible and transferable.
- Can be manipulated to take many fishes at a time
- Can easily tear.
- Cannot withstand harsh weather conditions.

v. Cages/Pens

- High water quality is ensured.
- Natural food is available
- Parasite and pests cannot easily be controlled.
- Pouching is very easy.

vi. **Wooden Tanks**

- Can be transferred.
- Supervision is easy.
- Water can easily destroy the wood.
- Large number of fish cannot be raised.

1.7 ECONOMY OF ACQUISITION

i. **Earthen pond**

- Easy to construct, one need only labour provided he owns the land.
- Big size pond can be easily constructed and raise many fish.

ii. **Concrete pond**

- It is expensive to build.
- Last longer, therefore can be reused over time
Plastic/Fibre glass
- Cheap to buy
- Cannot take many fish therefore it is not very economical.

iii. **Tarpaulin**

- It is not very costly.
- It doesn't last long.

iv. **Cages/Pens**

- It is cheap to construct.
- Need consistent repair after a single use.

v. **Wooden Tanks**

- Easy and cheap to make
- It doesn't last.

1.8 MAINTENANCE OF THE CULTURE FACILITIES

i. Earthen pond

- Slope the sides.
- Plant grasses on the dike.

ii. Concrete pond

- Always check for cracks and repair them.
- Maintain water quality through changing flow through.

iii. Plastic/ Fiberglass.

- Keep in a shaded place.
- Prevent putting heavy items on top.

iv. Tarpaulin

- Set it under a shed.
- Do not move it when fill with water.

v. Cage/ Pens

- When lifting do it gently.
- Do not pull the cage/ pen when fully set.
-

vi. Wooden tank

- Set under a shed.
- Do not attempt to lift it when set up

1.9. FISH FARM SITE SELECTION AND CONSTRUCTION

i. Homestead Fish Pond: For homestead fish culture, the house backyard is suitable. Earthen/Concrete pond can be used for this purpose. Soil at site of the earthen pond should be able to retain water.

ii. Commercial Fish Farm: In commercial fish farming, the first requirement is the choice of a suitable land for the establishment of the farm. Such a land must be sited near water with adequate topography for pond construction. The water source can be river/stream, spring, well or borehole. The water must be free from pollutants. Water is the medium for culturing fish; as a result the supply of water must be guaranteed throughout the culture period. The topography of the land should not be too hilly or too flat. A slightly depressed marshy land that can retain water for a long time is ideal for pond construction. Soils that are too porous or too clayey are not good for fish culture. In sandy soils, the water retention capacity is very low, while a soil that has very high proportion of clay (above 40% composition) will make the pond turbid (concentration of suspended solids) for fish. A suitable soil is that which has a good proportion of clay and loam (i.e. 40%: 60%)

1.10 LAND SURVEY AND FISH FARM DESIGN

Once a suitable land has been acquired, a registered Surveyor should survey it and a topographic map produced to permit the design of fishponds and other structures. The design of a fish farm varies with the nature of the land. If the slope is gentle enough (a good valley of 1:2 slope) to permit channels of water from the stream or river into the farm the construction of a storage reservoir may not be necessary. In most gently sloping valleys, channels may not be practicable hence it might be necessary to block the course of water in order to raise the water level to permit diversion into ponds lined along (parallel to) the course of the river or stream. Such a dam may not necessarily form a storage reservoir suitable for fish production because of the fast flowing nature of the river during the flood and the difficulty of screening off the fish.

1.11 HINTS ON POND CONSTRUCTION

After conducting a feasibility study and planning on the type and size of pond to build on the site selected, construction work can start. Depending on the nature of the surrounding land, the construction could be manual or mechanical. In marshy lands the use of heavy equipment is not advisable. This is due to the risks and

difficulties of using such equipment in those kinds of terrain. Construction of a large farm may require the services of an aquaculture engineer or a technical expert from any fisheries institution.

The main parts of any fish pond to be constructed are the dam walls (dikes), the water inlet and outlet system. Pond dikes must be well compacted to prevent seepage. Concrete ponds are preferable in areas where the soil is too sandy for earthen ponds or enough land is not available or the pond is required within the living premises. Cost of construction of concrete ponds vary with the size of pond, location, availability and cost of labor, source of water and cost of inputs such as cements, sand, gravel, plastic pipes, solid blocks, etc.

1.12 GENERAL CONSIDERATIONS IN SELECTING SUITABLE SITES FOR POND CONSTRUCTION

- Water supply must readily available to pond. If water is pipe borne, the chlorine content must be allowed to escape by storing in open tank for atleast 2 hours before use
- Security: The site must be protected nocturnal enemies of fish like frog, birds and domestic waste.
- Availability of labour both skilled and unskilled
- Availability of inputs such as fingerlings feeds and drugs.
- Marketing fish to be grown should attract high market price.
-

1.13 PLANNING THE POND

The following are useful lists in planning

- The shape and size of the pond should fit in with the topography of the land
- The pond bottom should slope for easy drainage i.e. 1:2
- The size of the homestead should not exceed 0.01ha for easy management. However, more than one of such pond size can be constructed if there is space
- The depth should not exceed 1-1.2m for homestead fish pond
- The water inlet should be constructed above the pond.

1.14 CONSTRUCTING THE POND

The general steps in construction is outlined as follows

- Visual survey of the site for topography and water supply
- Marking out pond area to measure length and breadth using tapes, ropes and pegs
- Excavating the marked out area based on specification
- Sandcrete blocks are laid to form the pond walls that would eventually hold water to height of 1.2m
- The pond floor is constructed to slope towards the deeper end to ensure water drainage by gravity
- Pond inlets are constructed using plastic pressure pipes from source usually over head and raised above ponds can help aeration
- Pond outlet is constructed at the lower end of the pond using plastic pipe and screened on inner part of pond and a gate valve on the outer part.

1.15 HOMESTEAD/COMMERCIAL FISH POND CONSTRUCTION COST ITEMS

Construction cost items are difficult to estimate since prices of inputs are unstable and vary from place to place. The information below will assist in arriving at a useful estimate depending on pond size and location.

- Cost of labour to excavate the land to required depth
- Cost of blocks
- Cost of cement, sand and gravel
- Cost of construction of pond walls and floor
- Cost of pipes for water inlet and outlet
- Cost of plumbing
- Cost of fingerlings to be stocked
- Cost of feeds e.g. grains bran, G/lake, fish meal etc.

1.16 POND PREPARATION FOR STOCKING

Before stocking the ponds the pond need to be prepared ready for stocking the desired fish these preparation may include the following after construction especially for earthen ponds and for extensive management scheme.

1.17 POND FERTILIZATION

Two types of fertilizers can be used to stimulate natural productivity in fishponds. These are organic manure and inorganic manure or chemical fertilizers (application rates for are shown in Table 1)

TABLE 2: Application Rate for Chemical Fertilizers

Fertilize Type	Application Rate	Comments
1.Basic Slag(15%of P2 O5)	36kg/ha/month	Apply 1 week after liming
2.Triple supper phosphate (T.S.P)	60kg/ha/month 300-	Apply twice monthly Apply twice monthly
3.Ammonium Sulphate (A.S)	400kg/ha/month	Apply monthly for 4 months
4. Mixture of TSP and AS.	133- 238kg/ha/month	

Fertilizer helps in enriching water nutrients for plankton production on which fish feed. There should be regular application of fertilizer to keep the water colour green. Bright green colour indicates that the pond is fertile (rich in organic nutrients). With availability of highly nutritious fish feeds e.g. Coppens, Alaqua, Euro feeds, Dizengof, e.t.c the use of fertilizer is not necessary in plastic tanks, concrete tanks and small earthen ponds.

1.18 LIMING PRACTICES

Liming is the process of application of agricultural/industrial limes to earthen ponds. If pond soil/or water is not acidic, liming may not be necessary. Soil and water may be tested in a laboratory or with a water analysis kit to determine whether liming is required.

Liming of fishponds is important for the following reasons: -

- Liming corrects the acidity of pond water to the suitable PH 6–9 for fish growth.
- Lime makes available phosphorus added in fertilizer for plant use. Phosphorus promotes the growth of algae (the microscopic plants) which are the base of natural fish food production in ponds.
- Lime acts as disinfectants of pond bottom, especially in new ponds or ponds in fallow.
- Lime helps in reducing water turbidity i.e. in settling soil particles in muddy ponds.

i. How to Apply Lime

Lime can be applied to pond bottom before impoundment-in filling with water- (pre-impoundment) or to a flooded pond (post-impoundment).

ii. Precautions

- Wear protective clothes and shoes (rain boots) in applying lime to pond bottom.
- As much as possible, avoid inhaling the lime dust. This is dangerous to health.
- After application, take a bath.

Liming materials good for fish ponds include: - Limestone/Agricultural lime – CaCO_3 , Caustic/slacked or hydrated lime - $\text{Ca}(\text{OH})_2$, Quicklime – CaO

Agricultural lime is the best liming material for fishpond. It is also the cheapest and readily available. They are by-products that can be obtained from cement factories.

iii. Liming Rates

The recommended liming rates using agricultural lime is shown below in Table 2.

TABLE 3: Liming Rates of Pond Using Agricultural Lime

Soil Type	New Ponds	Old Ponds
1 Clay soil	1680 - 2240kg/ha/year	1120kg/ha/year
2 Sandy soil	1120 - 1680kg/ha/year	560 1120kg/ha/year

iv. Tips for Maintenance of Fish ponds

Pond maintenance is what every pond owners have to put up with over a period of time. These may include the following

- Cleaning pond pipes, replacing old valves, for the inlets and outlets.
- Weed and algae control.
- Control of predators like frogs, snakes, and birds.
- Monitoring fish health.
- Maintenance of high water quality by flushing the ponds at regular intervals
- Avoid overstocking of fish ponds.
- Remove the decayed plants from pond bottom to keep up safety of aquatic life.
- Maintain the water level in your pond such that they stay in the right limits both in rainy and dry seasons.

1.19 PRODUCTION AND HANDLING OF FISH FINGERLINGS

INTRODUCTION

Fingerlings of fish from the wild for fish culture are very few and their strains are uncertain. For aquaculture to grow faster in Nigeria there is need to produce fast growing reliable fingerlings to serve the teaming fish fanners. Investment in fingerling production is therefore prompted by the following considerations; the need of fingerlings by commercial fish fanner to stock their ponds adequately and on time, to produce fingerlings in commercial quantity to serve their farms and

disposed excess to other needy farmers who may not have the facilities and technical know-how for such production. Intensive production of fingerlings can only be carried out under controlled condition in either indoor or outdoor hatchery systems. Hatcheries are used to produce fry or fingerlings for stocking fish ponds. A hatchery can also be used as a breeding centre for genetic improvement of fish stock. Many catfish and tilapia farmers who are engaged in food fish production find that an adequate supply of fingerlings is not always available. As long as the demand for fingerlings exists, a well-managed hatchery can be a lucrative business, farmers are therefore encouraged to set up their own hatcheries to produce fingerlings either for themselves or for sale. As the industry expands, the importance of having a reliable supply of high-quality fingerlings will become more apparent.

Figure 14: Fingerlings in a Plastic Bowl

1.20 GENERAL HATCHERY CONSIDERATIONS

i. Hatchery design

When designing the hatchery, the most important consideration is the water supply, including both its quantity and its quality.

The hatchery design should incorporate a good filtration system to improve water quality, reduce any pollution, and prevent the entry of predators such as insect larvae.

Farmers are advised to site their hatcheries on a slope so that water can flow into the hatchery by gravity. Sites should therefore have good soil characteristics and a suitable land gradient.

All incoming water should be filtered. Alternatively, only ground water should be used where possible.

Where possible, tanks, incubators, troughs, and other receptacles should be movable to allow for future modification.

If earthen ponds are to be constructed as part of the hatchery, then sandy or gravelly soils should be avoided. An impervious soil (i.e., one with sufficient clay content) will hold water and prevent seepage.

Land that is gently sloped provides drainage and allows the construction of raceways in a series for reuse of water by gravity flow.

ii. Hatchery equipment

Containers for rearing the fish are the major item needed. Examples include small buckets, long trays or troughs, aquaria, and large circular or oval tanks. You can use containers made from plastic, glass, or wooden materials.

Other items include weighing scale, netting materials, ruler, towels, trays, syringes and needles, sharp knife, mortar, pair of scissors, salt solution, thermometers, glassware or plastic basins (various sizes), and brushes.

iii. Rearing facilities

Rearing units include small tanks or troughs for swim-up fry, intermediate-size rearing tanks for fingerlings, and large outdoor rearing ponds or raceways. Rearing units should be constructed so they can be drained quickly and independently.

Rearing units should be adequate not only for the normal everyday water flow in the hatchery, but also for increased volumes of water needed during draining and cleaning of the facilities.

iv. Broodstock selection and maintenance

Select quality broodstock to improve fish production on your farm.

Choose pure quality stocks and do not allow them to crossbreed with other strains to preserve their genetic quality.

Teach your workers the importance of preventing genetic contamination.

Initially you may have to collect your broodstock from the wild, whereas later you can select them from your own ponds or purchase them from other farmers.

If buying your fish stocks from others, buy them only from reliable and established sources and avoid introducing breeders from non-accredited sources.

Use brood fish that are mature but not too old; for catfish and tilapia they should be at least one year old but not more than three years old (> 100 g for tilapia and between 0.5 and 1.0 kg for catfish).

By using larger brood fish, you can easily identify the original stock after each production cycle.

You can use the same stock repeatedly, depending on their performance, but should adopt a culling/selection process to eliminate undesirable stock.

Always eliminate fish that have questionable characteristics by examining breeders carefully when re-stocking after each cycle.

1.21 STOCKING YOUR FISH POND

Stock your ponds or tanks with the following numbers of fish:

For all-male (monosex) culture of tilapia for the market, stock fish of 20-40 g size in properly prepared ponds at a density of 1-2 fish per m².

If only mixed-sex tilapia are available to you, stock them as you would all-male fingerlings (i.e., at 1-2 fish per m²), but stock catfish fingerlings along with them. For every 1000 tilapia fingerlings stocked you should stock 50-100 catfish fingerlings (5-10% by number). At the time of stocking, the tilapia fingerlings should be four times bigger than the catfish fingerlings so that they cannot be eaten by the catfish. Later the catfish will help control the

tilapia population by consuming small tilapia that begin to appear when the tilapia you originally stocked reach spawning age (about 3 months).

If you plan to rear tilapia fry to fingerling size, either for further stocking or for hand sexing, stock 1-3 g fish in properly prepared nursery ponds at 10 fish per m².

Catfish

If you are stocking catfish finger lings to rear to market size, stock them at a density of from 2 to 5 per m². Stocking with the lower number (2/m²) should give you fish of up to 500 g each after 6-9 months of culture. Stocking at the higher density will give you smaller fish over the same rearing period, resulting in perhaps 200-250 g fish, depending on water temperatures and the amount of care you give to the pond.

For nursing to fingerling size, stock catfish fry in tanks or aquaria at 50-150 fry/ L. Nurse them in the aquaria or tanks for at least 14 days and then move them out to ponds or hapas, and stock at a density of 100 fry/m² and rear them for another 35-40 days.

Follow these guidelines for safe handling and movement of fish:

Stop feeding your fish one to two days prior to moving them.

Handle fish only during the cool parts of the day, preferably early in the morning.

Use seines and dipnets manufactured from the softest 'netting material possible to minimize abrasion to your fish.

Periodically inspect your tubs, dipnets, buckets, and other fish handling equipment to be sure there are no sharp edges or corners that can injure the fish.

Keep fish in water during all stages of moving from one place to another.

Do not crowd the fish too closely in seines, dip nets, tubs, or transport tanks.

Move fish to their next location as quickly as possible; do not leave tubs or buckets of fish out on the pond bank for a long time, especially on hot days.

When putting the fish into a pond, take some time to equalize the water temperature in the transfer container (plastic bag, bucket, tub, etc.) with that of the pond water. This can be done by floating the transfer container in the pond water for approximately 15 minutes prior to releasing the fish.

You can also gradually mix the pond water into the transfer container; this has the advantage of equalizing not only the water temperatures but also other water chemistry differences that may exist.

Whenever possible, provide a spray or gentle flows of clean, fresh water to fish that are crowded together during handling.

Clean all of your fish handling equipment thoroughly after each use. This can be done by thoroughly rinsing it in clean water, picking all debris, fish, or other materials out of it, and drying it briefly in the sun. This helps preserve your equipment and minimize the spread of fish diseases.

1.22 CATFISH SEED PRODUCTION

Broodfish maintenance

Maintain a conditioning/fattening pond of about 100-200 m² for your broodfish. This size of pond will hold 300 brooders (150 males and 150 females).

The pond should be sufficiently deep—about 1.0 to 1.5m.

Prior to filling and stocking the pond, fertilize it with organic or inorganic fertilizers to maintain its natural food production. Also apply lime in areas where the pond waters are acidic.

Feed your broodfish with a 40% crude protein feed three times a day at 1% of their body weight. Whenever possible it is advisable to stock small tilapia with the brooders to serve as supplemental food.

Stop feeding the broodfish one day prior to collecting them for spawning.

Spawning

1. Selection and handling of brooders

Capture and transport fish early in the morning or late in the evening when it is cool. Ice can be used to reduce sudden changes in water temperature.

Anesthetics have also been used to reduce fish stress during transportation and transfer to tanks.

Handle your broodfish as little and as gently as possible to avoid stress.

Damage to the slime (mucus) layer can lead to infection.

Use a seine to gently capture enough fish to be able to select sufficient males and females for

After collection of the fish from the conditioning pond, disinfect them in a formalin bath to prevent the transfer of pathogens from fish to eggs and fry.

Selection involves separating males from females and checking for maturity.

Do this by gently pressing the abdomen with the thumb; fecund females release shiny greenish eggs. Mature males cannot be stripped and can only be selected by their size.

Choose females of about 0.5 to 1.0 kg; this size has a substantial quantity of eggs and is easier to handle than larger fish.

For each female use at least two males of the same total weight.

2. Collecting and injecting the pituitary

To avoid temperature shock it is advisable to use a thermostat or heater where available.

Brooders should be held without food for 24-36 hours in a container at 25-30°C prior to injection with pituitary.

Pituitary can be collected from either male or female fish.

For each female spawner, two pituitary donors of 500 g average weight are used.

When using fresh pituitary, kill and decapitate donors less than an hour before planned injection. Open the palate of the mouth with a pair of pincers and locate the pituitary just below the ventral side of the brain.

Collect pituitary from the donor and place it in a mortar containing 2 ml physiological salt solution (9 g salt in 1 litre water).

Grind the pituitary, mixing it well with the saline solution.

Alternatively, pituitary can be stored for months in 1 ml acetone in a cool dry place to be used later.

Using a syringe with a needle 25 to 3.0 cm long and a diameter of 0.7mm, draw the pituitary suspension and prepare to inject the fish.

Cover the head with a hand towel and insert the needle at an angle of 45 degrees in the dorsal muscle. Inject and finger-rub the intramuscular area to distribute the suspension evenly.

Place the fish back in the container and wait for about 12 hours until all eggs have matured.

During ovulation, the belly of the female will swell due to water absorption of the ovary. If the female has responded well, eggs will easily run out from the genital papilla when the belly is gently pressed.

3. Stripping the female and fertilizing the eggs

Gently strip eggs from the female into a dry bowl and estimate the number of eggs (One gram contains about 600-700 eggs).

Male gonads can be removed and macerated (mashed) and the milt mixed with eggs at the time of stripping the female.

Squeeze the freshly dissected testes and distribute the milt droplets evenly.

Immediately add some clean water to the bowl and mix eggs with the sperm by gentle swirling of the bowl.

Use a feather to mix the eggs and milt.

Incubating the eggs

Pour the fertilized eggs into an incubating tray in a single layer. Within a few minutes after fertilization, the eggs will absorb water and sticky attachment discs will develop.

Incubate the eggs in flowing water with a flow-through rate of 1-3 litres per minute.

Healthy developing eggs have a transparent greenish-brown colour whereas dead eggs are white; dead eggs must be removed immediately to avoid fungal infection.

Depending on ambient water temperature, eggs will take 20-57 hours to hatch.

Where a screen is used to incubate eggs, hatchlings will fall to the bottom upon hatching. They can also be siphoned out into a tank where they will rest as they absorb their yolk.

Hatchlings must be separated from the egg shells to avoid infections that can lead to mortality. At this stage of development, the hatching rate will be about 50-80%.

Hatched fry are 5-7mm in length and weigh about 1.2-3.0 mg. They look like tiny needles with a green globe, the yolk-sac.

Due to the weight of the yolk-sac, hatchlings will fall to the bottom of the container. They will cluster together in dark places in the tank and will require a cover and aeration.

Within 3 days the yolk sac will be absorbed and the swim-up fry will start to search for food. With good management, 90-95% of the larvae will survive and develop into fry.

Transfer fry in buckets to weaning tanks or nursery ponds (weaning tanks preferred).

Larval Rearing

Several factors are of great importance when nursing catfish larvae:

Start them out in a protected hatchery environment (rather than stocking them directly into ponds) to increase survival rates.

Stock them at an appropriate density (about 100 larvae per litre) to get better growth and survival.

Availing large quantities of zooplankton (for example, rotifers or *Artemia*) as starter feeds for the first 10-14 days helps increase growth and survival rates.

Transfer the fry to hapas (feed well with live and artificial feeds) or to a well prepared (zooplankton rich) nursery pond to increase survival.

1. Hatchery rearing

After removal of dead eggs from the incubation trays or screens, transfer the live yolk-sac larvae to tanks or aquaria in the hatchery for further rearing.

Rear the young fish in the hatchery for 7 to 14 days (depending on water temperature) to achieve optimal survival when they are later transferred to nursery ponds.

Stock the larvae at a density of about 100 larvae per litre of water.

Maintain the water temperature at about 28°C.

Feed the larvae as much as they will eat in 15 minutes every two hours (around the clock) during the hatchery phase (about 14 days).

With this management you can expect a highly acceptable growth rate and a survival rate of 80% or better at a low cost.

2. First feeding of catfish larvae

Catfish larvae normally begin feeding on the second or third day after hatching, before the yolk sac is completely absorbed; therefore you must begin to feed them at this same time when rearing them in the hatchery.

When they begin feeding, the larvae normally utilize live feeds and their systems are not sufficiently developed to utilize dry (manufactured) feeds; it is therefore recommended that dry feeds be supplemented with *Artemia* nauplii or rotifers during at least 3 of the 10 to 12 daily feedings for the first three to four days of feeding.

If an abundance of live food is available, maintain a constant concentration of live food organisms in the larval rearing system, as this greatly enhances their growth rate.

It has been shown that a continual supply of food produces the highest growth rates; you should therefore feed your larvae as much as they will consume in about 15 minutes by hand every 2 or 3 hours for 16 to 18 hours each day.

Feeding with live feeds such as *Artemia* nauplii or rotifers has advantages over dry feed; for example, the best growth is obtained when larvae are fed *Artemia* only (250 mg average weight after 11 days).

Feeding with *Artemia* nauplii or rotifers is stopped on the second or third day after the start of exogenous feeding, when the larvae are big enough to ingest inert food particles or zooplankton (usually *Daphnia*).

The larvae grow very rapidly after the start of feeding (about 100% body weight/day).

3. Predation on the larvae

One of the most serious predators in ponds is toad tadpoles. The presence of tadpoles is also a nuisance because they compete for food resources within the pond.

Other predators include backswimmers, insect larvae, copepods, etc.

It has been observed that predation pressure can be very high (100% mortality) during the yolk-sac stage but decreases gradually as the larvae increase in size.

It is therefore suggested that fry be transferred to nursing ponds only after they have reached a size greater than 10 mm to avoid losses to predation during the primary nursing phase.

4. Transferring catfish fry to nursery ponds

After approximately 14 days in hatchery tanks, the fry can be transferred to ponds.

Ponds should be well prepared to receive the fry. This includes proper pond bottom drying between crops, liming when needed, and proper fertilization to develop abundant supplies of natural foods for the fry to be stocked.

Where possible, use hapas in ponds to further protect your fry and increase their growth and survival rates. For best results, totally cover the tops of the hapas with cut grasses or other materials to provide the maximum possible amount of shade for the fry.

After 14 days in the hatchery, fry transferred to hapas or nursery ponds should be reared an additional 14 days, or until they reach a length of 2-3 cm.

This is a suitable size either for stocking into production ponds or for use as baitfish.

Factors contributing to the growth and survival of catfish fry

Factors that influence the growth and survival of catfish fry include:

Stocking density: High stocking densities result in poor growth and survival; low stocking densities enhance growth and survival, but are less economical.

Cover or shading: Cover and shading enhance growth and survival, whereas exposure to light lowers growth rates and increases mortality by contributing to increased cannibalism and stress.

Production period: Most mortalities occur during the early part of the nursing phase. The first 30-45 days is critical; thereafter survival is often close to 100%.

Cannibalism: Losses due to cannibalism can be minimized by providing cover (shade) and adequate amounts of high quality feed.

Predation: Predation by tadpoles significantly reduces survival.

Feeding: The availability of live feeds greatly reduces mortality.

MODULE 2

FISH FEEDS AND FEEDING

2.1 TYPES OF FISH FEEDS

Fish feed on a variety of foods. These include food produced from the natural pond environment and feeds given as supplement to the pond.

(a) Natural Fish Foods

Living organisms are natural fish foods and they are produced in the water where the fish live. Phytoplankton (microscopic plants), zooplankton (microscopic animals), and aquatic organisms like insects, crustacean, molluscs, and aquatic plants are all examples of natural foods. Fertilization increases their abundance.

(b) Supplementary Feeds

When natural foods are not available in sufficient quantity to provide adequate nutrition for fish growth, feeds that are manufactured or grown outside of the fish pond may be fed at regular intervals (daily, weekly, etc). These feeds supplement natural foods. Supplementary feeds should include finely divided artificial food like egg yolk, blood meal, fish meal, shrimp flour, bean flour, oil cakes, bone meals, cereal brans, etc. Adult fish prefer feeds available in pellet form. Sinking pellets are more suitable to bottom feeders like *Clarias* and *Heterotis* spp., while for *Tilapia* (a surface feeder) floating pellets are suitable. Pelleted feed of not more than 3.2mm in diameter is suitable for fish species. It is recommended to feed fish with pellets since the fish will readily take the whole nutrients in the food. Good quality feed for fish farming purpose should have the following proximate composition - *Protein: 35%, Minerals and Vitamins: 32-33%, Fat: 11% and Carbohydrates: 6- 10%*.

Feed ingredients should be free of toxicants, e.g. Haemagglutins in raw soybeans and Gossypol in cotton seed meal. These toxicants can be removed by roasting the feed stuffs ingredients. In polyculture, the feeding habits of fish species stocked should be considered. A combination of species like *Tilapia*, *Clarias* and *Heterotis* in the same pond will require sinking and floating pellets/crushed meals.

Figure 15: Some imported floating fish feeds

2.2 HINTS FOR FEEDING FISH IN PONDS

1. Feed fish at definite points in the pond or by broadcasting. This will make the fish to respond more to feeding spots.
2. Feed fish on daily basis – best times are morning before 7.00 am and evening from 6.00pm. Irregular feeding will retard the growth rate of fish.
3. Avoid overstocking of pond with feeds. Overstocking can result in water pollution and death of fish. Feed fish according to the recommended rates.

2.3 FEEDING METHOD

Feeding can be done manually or mechanically by using different type of feeders such as demand feeders and automatic feeders. The simple and traditional method of feed presentation involves simply pouring the feed into the culture systems having cultured organisms. It's obviously labour intensive but holds the advantages of requiring low expenses and allows the farmer to monitor the cultured species at the time of feeding, especially in the case of use of floating pellets where the feed can be thrown in from scoops or buckets. Over the years numerous mechanical aids for hand feeding such as hand operated blowers and the disc throwers have been

invented. Fish should be fed at regular interval and only when they are hungry, also feeding spot has to be maintained. Care has to be taken to avoid leaving leftover of feed so as to prevent deterioration of water quality.

2.4 IDENTIFICATION OF LOCAL FEED INGREDIENTS

These include the feedstuff that are agro-industrial by-products and are commonly used in aquaculture. Most of these feed ingredients are cheaply and easily available throughout the year. Their usage is standardized and is widely accepted. They can be either of animal or plant origin e.g. wheat bran, groundnut cake, rice bran, maize, soyabean meal, cotton seed meal, rice husk, cassava meal, fish meal, shrimp meal, blood meal and bone meal etc.

2.5 COMPOUNDING FISH FEED

Diet formulation represents translation of nutrient and energy requirements of a given species for a given response into an acceptable diet using a balanced mixture of ingredients which is economically sustainable. Basics of formulation involves blending or mixing of different combinations of nutritionally rich feed ingredients to get nutritionally balanced and economically sound diet that can be used in required amount to provide the level of production desired in aquaculture. Although there are a number of ingredients available, the choice of these ingredients should be based on the nutritional value taking into account potential anti-nutritional factors rather than merely on the basis of cost per unit weight alone. Formulations should be based on available nutrient and energy required.

2.6 PELLETIZING FISH FEED

There are two forms in which pellets can be manufactured and fed. Moist pelleted feeds have higher water contents than the dry form of pellets and therefore are more susceptible to damage by fungal and bacterial growth. Extrusion technology though more expensive and technically demanding has become more and more common in the aquaculture industry. The process involves pushing the mixture of feed ingredients through an extruder which is a machine with a long barrel with a single

hole under pressure. When the material exits through the extruder barrel, it is cut into pellets and dried sometimes. Extrusion or expansion processes improve nutritional properties of the finished feeds and decrease the level of anti-nutritional factors and bacterial counts in the finished feed. Feed ingredients rich in starch when passed through the extruder under sufficient high temperature and pressure cause expansion of starches due to the trapped air and result floating pellets whilst process with lower heat and pressure can give a sinking pellet.

2.7 STORAGE OF FISH FEED

Manufactured feed should be stored in bags in a cool and dry place. In case the manufactured feed is going to be used immediately, then the chances of spoilage by fungi and algae are reduced considerably stored feed is often attracted by and destroyed by a number of organisms such as bugs, mice, and rats so the bags should be stored in a secure location. Bagged feed should generally be used within 90 days after purchase. The feed should be arranged properly in order of the date purchased or manufactured to avoid spoilage.

MODULE 3

WATER QUALITY MANAGEMENT

3.1 INTRODUCTION

Water quality for aquaculturist refers to the quality of water that enables successful propagation of fish. The required water quality is determined by the specific organisms to be cultured and has many components that are interwoven. Sometimes a component can be dealt with separately, but because of the complex interaction between components, the composition of the total array must be addressed. Growth and survival, which together determine the ultimate yield, are influenced by a number of ecological parameters and managerial practices. High stocking densities of fish in ponds usually exacerbates problems with water and sediment deterioration. Wastes generated by aquaculture activity (faeces and unconsumed feed) first settle in the bottom, as a consequence of organic matter is accumulated in settlement and water. Part of the waste is flushed out of the ponds immediately or late after the organic matter has been degraded. In an intensive system of culture salinity, PH, and DO are the main parameters which demonstrate fluctuation. In addition, ammonia-N increased exponentially with culture period. Low DO level is the major limiting water quality parameter in aquaculture systems. A critically low DO levels occurs in ponds particularly when algae blooms die-off and subsequent decomposition of algae blooms and can cause stress or mortality of fish in ponds. Chronically low dissolved oxygen levels frequency. Another major consequence of aquaculture production is a high degree of variability in the concentration of dissolved nitrites and ammonia. High feeding rates in fish farms leads to eutrophic conditions characterized by substantial phytoplankton blooms. The environmental conditions that create high ammonia concentrations may also cause increases in nitrite concentration. Both ammonia and nitrite can be directly toxic to culture organisms or can induce to sub lethal stress in culture populations that result in lower resistance to diseases.

3.2 DISSOLVED OXYGEN (DO)

Dissolve oxygen is the most critical and limiting factor in aquaculture. Oxygen enters water through photosynthesis by aquatic plants, principally phytoplankton, and by diffusion at the air-water interface. Oxygen is lost from the water through respiration by fish, phytoplankton and other organisms, and by aerobic decay of organic matters. The signs fish exhibit to how dissolve oxygen (D.O) include: loss of appetite, lethargy, gasping near the surface of the pond, fish facing into current of inlet or aeration death of larger fish, followed by smaller fish. The effects of low DO include: stress increased susceptibility to diseases, poor feed conversion efficiency, poor growth and death of fish and other aquatic organisms. The following causes low DO large blooms of phytoplankton, zooplankton and other pond organisms, high stocking densities of fish and high feeding rates, excessive turbidity, serious cloudy, windless days and combination of above factors. To rectify low DO the following measures should be taken: monitor DO routinely and chart diurnal fluctuations to predicts periods of low DO, maintain aeration day and night, provide additional aeration, spray water across the pond surface, use tractor PTO run paddle wheels or sprayers, stop or reduce feeding, exchange water and remove dead plant and animal material from the water.

Figure 16: DO Meter

3.3 pH

This is the measure of the hydrogen ion concentration in soil or water. An ion is an electrically charged atom. Water exists as a balance between hydrogen ions (H^+) and hydroxyl ions (OH^-). The pH of pond water should be maintained between the optimum limits for fish that is 6.5-9.0 if the water is too acidic, lime should be applied and when it is too basic, fertilizer should be applied according to recommended dosage. When the pH is sub-optimal, there will be increase of mucus on gill surfaces damage to eye lens and cornea, abnormal swimming behaviour, fin ray, poor phytoplankton and zooplankton and death. The effect of sub-optimal pH include: stress, increased susceptibility to disease, low production levels and poor growth. Sub-optimal pH are caused by acidic water and soils, acid sulphate soils, poorly buffered water, waters having high alkalinity and low hardness, acid rain. To increase pH you have to; flush the pond, reduce feeding rates to lower nutrient input and plant growth, ponds built in acid sulphate soils should be refilled lime directly to prevent drying, built no deeper than necessary, grassed on the walls, limed on the walls, add gypsum to increase calcium concentration, Alum for immediate reduction of pH to avert imminent fish mortality. To increase pH: lime the ponds, increase phytoplankton abundance by fertilizing.

Figure 17: pH Meter

3.4 TEMPERATURE

Aquaculture organisms are cold blooded animals. They can modify their body temperature to the environment in normal condition, unlike the warm-blood animals, which can react to maintain the optimum range of temperature. For example, the optimum range of temperature for the black tiger head shrimp is _____

between 28⁰c-30⁰c. Increase in temperature beyond 30⁰c increase the activity level and the metabolism. This also increases the growth rate. If the temperature still increases then the shrimp reacts a threshold of physical and nutritional tolerance, which is 33⁰c in poor quality H₂O or 35⁰c in good quality water and remains stationary at the pond bottom.

If the environment does not improve the culture organisms may get infected by germs, swim in a disoriented way to the surface or due to exhaustion. If the temperature falls below 28⁰c, the metabolism reduces and so does the active behaviour and growth rate. Below 20⁰c, the shrimp will take less feed. Shrimps cannot tolerate a temperature less than 13⁰c. Water depth and water volume affect the thermal capacity of the pond and the extent of light penetration. It is related to fluctuation of planktonic algae and benthic algae. It also influences the volume of the pond and therefore the ponds capacity to support the dissolved oxygen, influencing productivity, biomass and production yield.

Figure 18: Thermometer

3.5 AMMONIA

Ammonia is the major waste product of protein or nitrogenous metabolism in fish and other aquatic organisms. The major source of nitrogen compounds in fish pond culture is the protein. Ammonia monitoring contained in the feed. Therefore, the rate of ammonia production is proportional to the feeding rate. It is excreted primarily across the gills, and in urine and faeces. Ammonia is also produced during the aerobic decomposition of organic matter by bacteria. In water, the total ammonia nitrogen occurs in two forms, unionized ammonia (NH₃) which is toxic to fish, and the ammonium ion (NH₄) which is relatively non toxic except at extremely

high concentrations. Ammonia can change from one form to the other creating a balance between the two forms. Water pH and temperature influence the proportion of total ammonia occurring as the toxic form. Signs of high ammonia include: abnormal swimming behaviour including lethargy, reduced feeding, congregation around water inlet or pond edges and fish showing above signs in the afternoon but recovering during the night. Effects of high ammonia include: gill damage reduced growth rate, increased susceptibility to disease elevated blood pH, tissue and internal organ damage poor osmoregulation and death. To correct high ammonia, you need to reduce or stop feeding flush pond, reduce stocking density, aerate the pond and in emergencies, reduce the pH of the pond.

3.6 NITRITE

Nitrite (NO_2) is a product of bacterial reduction of ammonia. Nitrite replaces oxygen in the blood to form methaemoglobin. When concentrations of methaemoglobin in catfish blood reach 20-30%, the gill filaments become chocolate brown colour and fish are diagnosed as having —brown blood —disease, brown blood often occurs in the fall, even if the ponds are not heavily stocked. Behavioural signs of fish with —brown blood disease are the same as ammonia toxicity. Affected fish do not respond to blood aeration. Catfish ponds sometimes contain 0.5-50 ppm or more of NO_2 , and nitrite is especially dangerous when halving fish. Channel catfish may die when water contains 4.5-13ppm NO_2 . Tilapias are more tolerant of NO_2 than catfish, and centrarchids are very resistant to NO_2 toxicity. Nitrite can be controlled by adding calcium (agricultural limestone) to soft water or by adding salt to both soft and hard H_2O .

3.7 CARBONDIOXIDE AND HYDROGEN SULPHIDE

CO_2 is a by product of aerobic respiration. It levels in fish culture ponds cycle daily, with highest levels near dawn and lowest levels in mid-afternoon. Fish affected by CO_2 becomes listless, and then lie motionless on the pond bottom. Affected fish usually recover rapidly after aeration. H_2S is excreted by bacteria during an aerobic decomposition of waste products on the pond bottom. Any detectable level should

be considered detrimental to fish production. Hydrogen sulphide smells like rotten eggs, hence may be easily detected. Hydrogen sulphide may cause water to appear grey, and then suddenly clear within a few hours, with a black film on the pond bottom and vegetation. Control of H₂S is achieved by maintaining oxygen at all depths in culture ponds. Also, the water should be aerated, circulated, or maintained at depths no greater than 6ft.

3.8 ALGAE AND PLANKTON

Plankton comprises all the microscopic organisms that are suspended in water and includes small plants (phytoplankton) and small animals (zooplankton) and bacteria. When there is enough plankton in the water to discolour it, then water is said to contain plankton –bloom because plankton forms the base of the food web, there is strong relationship between plankton abundance and fish production. Plankton blooms are a common feature of fish culture ponds. Excessive phytoplankton blooms can also cause large diurnal fluctuations in water quality variables, such condition are stressful to fish. They are undesirable in fish ponds because they: interfere with fish management such as feeding and harvesting, they compete with fish for nutrients, contribute to oxygen depletion and high ammonia levels when they decompose, they contribute to water loss through evapotranspiration, they also provide haven for undesirable fish. Management options to reduce them include: drying and desilting of ponds, mechanical harvesting, and application of herbicides.

3.9 TURBIDITY

Water turbidity refers to the quantity of suspended material, which interferes with light penetration in the water column. In ponds, water turbidity can result from planktonic organisms or from suspended decay particles. Turbidity limits light penetration, thereby limiting photosynthesis in the bottom layer. Higher turbidity can cause temperature and DO stratification in fish ponds planktonic organisms is desirable when not excessive, but suspended decay particles are undesirable. It can cause clogging of gills or direct injury to tissues of fish. Alum and ferric sulphate are

effective in removing decay turbidity. They also have acid reactions and can depress pH and total alkalinity.

3.10 SALINITY

Salinity plays an important role in the growth of culture organisms through osmo-regulations of body minerals from that of the surrounding water for example the optimum range of salinity for black tiger shrimp is between 10-25 ppt, although the shrimp will accept salinity between 5 and 38ppt. since its environmental character. The early life stages of both shrimp and prawn require standard sea water salinities but while growing they can withstand to brackish water or even to fresh water. However for better survival and growth, optimum range of salinity should be maintained in the culture ponds.

3.11 WATER QUALITY MONITORING

It is advisable for the fish farmer to constantly monitor the quality and quantity of pond water. Some indicators of bad quality of water are:

- Offensive odour

- Thick, deep green, brownish or greyish colour

- Sluggish movement of fish

- Off appetite and poor feed consumption

- Fish death

The first aid treatment is to flush out the water and replace it immediately. Water kit can be used to monitor Ph, dissolved oxygen, temperature etc. The walls of concrete, plastic, tarpaulin, metal and wooden tanks should be regularly cleaned of algal growth and food particles to avoid pollution and fish death.

CONCLUSION

In conclusion, the maintenance of good water quality is essential for both survival and optimum growth of culture organisms. The levels of metabolites in pond water that can have an adverse effect on growth are generally on order of magnitude lower than those tolerated by fishes for survival. Good water quality is characterized by adequate oxygen and limited levels of metabolites. The culture

organisms, algae and micro organisms such as bacteria produce metabolites in a pond. The major source of nutrients in aquaculture is the fee. Because large quantities of feeds are loaded in ponds, excess feed, faecal matter and other metabolites become available in large quantities for the growth of algae and micro organisms.

MODULE 4

FISH HARVESTING AND PROCESSING

4.1 METHODS OF FISH HARVESTING

A proper harvesting is an important step in keeping fish and other cultured produce in a good condition, so that their survival and quality for other uses are assured. It should be carried out with care as it is an important handling procedure. If not carried out in proper way, it can cause stress to the cultured animals. Stress animals are prone to diseases and adverse physiological imbalances.

Three methods of harvesting of fish from ponds are common namely:

i. Harvesting by Draining all the Water

This practice can be carried out in the situations where there is sufficient water supply and the farmer can afford to drain the entire pond water and refill it after draining. This type of harvesting does not require the use of seine or gill nets and can be efficiently carried out with the help of a basket or hand nets.

ii. Harvesting by Draining Part of the Water

This method of harvesting involves opening the plug that is closing the outlet and allowing water to drain out slowly. Care should be taken to ensure that no culture fish could exit or escape when drainage is carried out. Afterward the water is replaced after blocking the outlet. This is followed by the actual harvesting process with the help of a seine net.

iii. Harvesting without Draining the Water

This type of harvesting is generally carried out with the help of a seine net, lift net, cast net or gill net. In this harvesting method only part of the culture fish are harvested.

4.2 POST-HARVEST PROCESSING OF FISH

i. Drying

It is one of the oldest and most widely used methods of preservation. Drying is based on the principle that reduction in the water content or its complete removal will proportionally retard or totally stop all microbial and autolytic activities, thus preventing spoilage and resulting in preservation. Drying of fish involves the removal of water from the solid fish body with the help of an input of thermal energy.

Figure 19: Fish Sun drying

ii. Smoking

Fish may be smoked whole or after splitting, gutting etc. the method employed being dependent on the end product desired. Large fish are gutted, headed and split or made into fillets. It's very important that the guts, gills, kidney etc are completely removed. These are the areas where spoilage can take place quickly and can affect the overall quality of the end product.

Figure 20: An Electrical Oven Smoking Kiln

iii. Freezing

This low temperature method of preservation is traditionally used for fish. By employing a correct freezing method, a long shelf life and a processed product quite similar to fresh fish can be ensured. Freezing works on the principle that lowering the temperature reduces the chemical and enzymatic reactions and lowers the rate of spoilage.

Figure 21: Fish Freezing

